

Book of Abstracts

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Monday, July 21, 2025: Poster Session One

Syntactic properties of classifier predicates in Polish Sign Language (PJM) – research challenges and initial results

Rafał Darasz
University of Warsaw

One of the most important areas of PJM (PJM, *polski język migowy*) syntax that has not yet received a comprehensive study is classifier predicates, which are composed of classifiers and morphemes denoting a referent's movement or location, or the handling of referents (Zwitserlood, 2012). An in-depth description of their syntactic properties has been made in few extensive analyses, one of them being a corpus-based study of clause-like units (CLUs – explained below) in Auslan (Hodge, 2013). I am currently conducting a study of syntactic properties of classifier predicates in PJM as a part of my PhD project. The research material comes from the Corpus of Polish Sign Language (Wójcicka et al., 2020) created by the Section for Sign Linguistics at the University of Warsaw, which is currently one of the world's largest annotated sign language corpora. For this study, I chose to analyze data from the comic strips retelling task, as it potentially includes a large number of utterances with classifier predicates. The crucial step is the annotation stage involving dividing the sign texts into clause-like units, finding the predicates and arguments, and assigning semantic roles to those elements. This part is currently underway and is one of the most challenging ones, that is why I want to present it as a part of my poster. Clause-like units (CLUs) are defined as “basic articulatory chunks of propositional meaning” (Johnston, 2019). Identifying and analyzing clause-like units in the PJM Corpus is based on a theoretical framework of composite utterances, lexicogrammar and clause linkage and on methods used by Hodge (2013). Predicates and arguments are being assigned semantic roles from the list proposed in the Auslan Corpus Annotation Guidelines (Johnston, 2019). The purpose of the annotation is to collect a comparable number of CLUs with and without classifier predicates (about 1000 in each category). Initial results will be shown, such as the tendencies related to positioning classifier predicates in the sentence-final position, which corresponds with patterns described cross-linguistically in Emmorey (2003) or related to using classifier predicates in stand-alone CLUs.

Language attitudes of Chilean deaf signers towards lexical variation in Chilean Sign Language

Verónica Escobar
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Chilean Sign Language (LSCh) is the primary language of the Chilean deaf community and exhibits lexical variation. However, awareness and attitudes toward this variation remain unclear. This study explores perceptions of lexical diversity in LSCh.

Research on language attitudes in sign languages is still emerging. Studies have examined general language attitudes (Burns et al., 2001; Krausneker, 2015; Hill et al., 2019) and perceptions of signing styles (Hill, 2012; Mitchiner, 2014), but few focus on regional variation. Ma (2020) analysed attitudes toward sign variants in Chinese Sign Language, while Rowley and Cormier (2021) explored regional perceptions in British Sign Language (BSL), finding high awareness and pride in local variants. Currently, there is no study on language attitudes in LSCh, making this research the first of its kind.

Data collection took place in four Chilean cities— Iquique, Santiago, Temuco, and Punta Arenas— chosen for their geographic diversity and sign variation. Sixteen adult participants (four per city) were interviewed by local fieldworkers, considering age, gender, family background, and teaching experience. Participants answered questions on regional differences, signing styles, age-related variation, technology's impact, and communication challenges.

The study employed Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006; 2021) to identify patterns in responses. Preliminary findings indicate strong awareness of lexical variation, parallels with spoken accents, and distinctions between younger and older signers, particularly in numeric signs. While comprehension remains high, concerns persist about borrowed signs from neighbouring countries potentially threatening LSCh's linguistic integrity.

The study underscores the need for continued research, involving deaf advisors and consulting dictionaries to preserve LSCh's linguistic heritage. Recognising both traditional and emerging signs is crucial for maintaining LSCh's cultural and linguistic richness.

Managing the representation of a translated deaf self in interpreted settings: Conceptualizing 'Doing Trust'

**Dina Zander-Tabbert
Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin**

Based on research on the 'translated deaf self' (Napier et al., 2020; Young et al., 2020) this study investigates the strategies employed by deaf professionals to manage and control their deaf self and representation in workplace environments involving sign language interpreters (SLI). Conducting field research, data was collected from four deaf professionals through participant observation and analyzed using the Grounded Theory Method (GTM) in MAXQDA. This resulted in inductive coding categories, which were used for the subsequent development of three semi-structured interviews. Analysis of the initial data from the first cycle identified trust as a central theme.

Trust has been widely discussed in relation to deaf people and sign language interpreters (de Wit & Sluis, 2014; Feyne, 2018). While SLIs view trust as essential for successful communication and take trust for granted, deaf professionals often perceive it as an implied expectation rather than a collaboratively constructed process (O'Brien et al., 2023). Research also highlights the inherent vulnerability of deaf users who have to rely on SLI and have no effective control over the interpreted message (De Meulder et al., 2018).

The first part of the study examines deaf professionals' strategies for managing their translated deaf self in interpreted environments. It draws on Luhmann's (2000) and Möllering's (2005) theories of trust, integrating Hille et al.'s (2021) concept of 'doing trust', which recognizes trust as an active, reciprocal process rather than a static assumption. This study is also inspired by trust building strategies in social work and counselling (Tipton, 2014). Illustrating the cyclical nature of 'doing trust' this model offers strategies for fostering trust through mutual engagement, contributing to a deeper understanding of the interpreted deaf self and providing practical insights for improving professional relationships between interpreters and deaf individuals.

Evaluating Sign Language Policy

Filipe Venade de Sousa

FD-UCP, ESE-IPP, JusGov, Universidade Aberta

Language Policy and Planning (LPP) is widely recognised for its decisive impact on the status, corpus, acquisition, and prestige of languages in general. Despite the legal recognition of sign languages in many countries, they face considerable challenges in the effective implementation of language policies (De Meulder et al., 2016; Krausneker, 2009). Legal recognition alone does not guarantee the realisation of inherent language rights (*e.g.* Skutnabb-Kangas & Phillipson, 2017).

This research aims primarily to analyse how the integration of sign languages into policy frameworks influences their practical effectiveness. Unlike spoken languages, which are often included in broader language policies, sign languages face legal and political ambiguities resulting from their inherent historical and social contexts (Tupi, 2019). In view of the above, it is essential to evaluate language policies that are in line with the sociolinguistic and sociopolitical realities of the sign languages in question, including national and regional sign languages. For example, in Spain, there is Spanish Sign Language throughout the territory and, on the other hand, Catalan Sign Language in Catalonia, with different inherent political implications (*e.g.* Cabeza Pereiro & Eijo Santos, 2018; Quer, 2012).

The methodology adopted for this analysis involves qualitative research (mainly documentary analysis) of sign language policies in four selected countries (Finland, Norway, Spain and Portugal, each with different sociopolitical contexts). These policies are mapped on the basis of language legislation and, above all, on the instruments of language policies at different levels of public intervention. The study is based on Grin's (2010) guiding principles for sign language policies — effectiveness, cost-effectiveness, democracy and feasibility — and Grin's (1999) framework of “capacity, opportunity and desire”, aiming to assess the effectiveness with which sign language communities can exercise their linguistic rights in everyday life.

Preliminary results indicate that, even in the presence of legal recognition, the absence of real conditions of use results in merely symbolic rights. A relevant policy model is the Finnish system of “Follow-up Indicators for Linguistic Rights” (Artemjeff; Lunabba, 2018), in which structural, process and outcome indicators are applied to monitor the implementation of language rights. This research argues for a broader policy agenda that includes the integration of sign languages into instruments such as the European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages (ECRML), to assess the appropriate levels of implementation of measures adopted by public authorities, in line with the essential parameters, and, furthermore, emphasizes the need for coherence and effectiveness of the language rights of sign language communities (*e.g.* Tupi, 2019).

Gallery and Museum Education in the Art Education of Deaf Pupils

Ivana Hay

Charles University of Prague

My poster presents my dissertation “***Gallery and Museum Education in the Art Education of Deaf Pupils***”, which examines how Deaf pupils in Czech Deaf schools engage with art education. The focus is on making cultural spaces like galleries and museums accessible and inclusive through educational partnerships. Deaf people are a cultural and linguistic minority with specific educational needs and rights. Integrating Deaf culture and Deaf art into art education is essential for identity development and empowerment. With support from the SYLFF scholarship, I conducted comparative research in the UK, Poland, and the USA. In the USA, the formal curriculum De’VIA (Deaf View/Image Art) helps Deaf and Deafblind students explore identity, advocacy, sign language, and rights through visual arts. It is also used in public schools for hearing students in ASL programs, promoting inclusivity and awareness. A key feature of De’VIA is Deafhood pedagogy, developed by Dr. Paddy Ladd, which fosters cultural identity and redefines disability in education. My research highlights this as a valuable model for curriculum development. The theoretical part of my dissertation explores visual literacy, Deaf identity, and accessibility in museum and gallery education. My fieldwork includes examples of good practice: Deaf-led exhibitions in the UK, Deaf curators at the Museum Śląskie in Poland, and educational programs at Gallaudet University and the National Technical Institute for the Deaf in the USA. These international insights inform my qualitative research in Prague, where I examine current practices in Deaf art education and assess opportunities to embed Deaf culture and art into the curriculum. My findings support the need for art education models that strengthen Deaf identity, improve accessibility, and recognize Deaf culture as a vital part of educational and cultural life.

Tuesday, July 22, 2025: Poster Session Two

On the interplay of manual and nonmanual negators in Turkish Sign Language (TİD): A corpus-based analysis

Hasan Dikyuva
University of Amsterdam

This study investigates the frequency and distribution of negation markers (both manual and nonmanual) in Turkish Sign Language (TİD). Negation, a universal linguistic phenomenon, demonstrates significant variation across signed languages (SLs), revealing unique typological patterns. For example, some SLs mainly employ nonmanual markers (NMMs) such as headshake, while others have been shown to rely mainly on manual negation signs. TİD has traditionally been classified as being the latter type, i.e., a manual dominant SL (Zeshan, 2006). The present study reassesses this classification from the perspective of corpus linguistic research.

Data for this study comes from a subset of an existing corpus (Dikyuva et al., 2017). Video recorded semi-structured conversations of 66 participants were further annotated for negative statements. We coded 1,418 negative clauses and identified sixteen manual negation signs and thirteen nonmanual markers. Regarding the interplay of manual negators and NMMs, three categories were distinguished: a) nonmanual marking only (81 / 1,418 cases: 5.72%); b) manual marking only (148 / 1,418: 10.37%); and c) combined use of manual negator and NMMs (1,189 / 1,418 cases: 83.91%). We will discuss the combined use of NMMs with the four most commonly found manual negators. Our findings clearly show that TİD negation is mostly expressed by using a combination of both manual negators and NMMs.

While our analyses seem to underscore TİD's classification as a manual-dominant SL, it is also clear that the majority of cases still included NMMs. The frequent co-occurrence of NMMs with manual negators further suggests that TİD features a hybrid system (Makaroğlu, 2021), thus challenging the traditional dichotomy. Our functional analysis of the role of NMMs in TİD negation thus sheds new light on discussions regarding the typology of TİD.

Directionality in simultaneous interpreting between German and German Sign Language (DGS): A comparison study between novice and experienced interpreters

Britta Durczok

Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

Background: In interpreting theory, there is a long-standing debate regarding directionality whether interpreters perform better into their first language(s) (L1)¹, also called A-language(s), or into their second language(s) (L2)², called B-language(s). Previously, signed language interpreters (SLI) reported a preference for working from a spoken language (L1) into a signed language, which for most is an L2. This study investigated whether SLI in Germany indicate a preference for an interpreting direction and if they show differences in interpreting performance for each direction.

Method: The study adapts the methodology of Nicodemus and Emmorey (2013³, 2015⁴) to the German context, combining questionnaire data on interpreter preferences with experimental performance measurements. Participants were novice interpreters (n = 10, mean professional experience: 1.55 years) and experienced interpreters (n = 10, mean professional experience: 14.8 years), who all acquired German as L1 and DGS as a late L2. The two groups were compared on: (1) questionnaire on interpreting direction preferences and (2) interpreting performance tasks in both directions, involving narrative and informative text types. Performances were evaluated for content accuracy and articulation quality.

Results: Unlike previous studies, participants showed no consistent directional preferences (40% of novices and 60% of experienced interpreters reported no preference). However, 70% of all participants predominantly interpreted from German into DGS in professional practice. Novice interpreters showed a significant directionality effect regarding content accuracy, performing better when interpreting from German into DGS ($p < .005$), while experienced interpreters showed balanced performance across directions. Text type significantly affected performance: novices achieved better accuracy for informative texts when interpreting DGS-to-German ($p < .01$) and better articulation quality for narrative texts when interpreting German- to-DGS ($p < .001$). Experienced interpreters showed better articulation quality for informative texts when interpreting from DGS to German ($p < .001$).

Conclusion/Discussion: The study reveals that directionality effects in bimodal interpreting are more complex than traditionally assumed, influenced by professional experience and text type. The absence of clear directional preferences among German SLI contrasts with international findings, possibly reflecting differences in training approaches. While novice interpreters showed better performance from German into DGS, experienced interpreters demonstrated balanced competencies in both directions, suggesting that experience helps overcome initial directional asymmetries. The differential effects of text types highlight the importance of incorporating diverse genres in interpreter training.

Through the eyes of sign languages (SLs) and their Deaf users

Andrea Lackner
University of Graz

When analyzing SLs, formerly and still a common way is to use elicited data. However, since introducing the technical options of creating SL corpora and making use of the various annotation and technical analytic tools, more prospects are provided for SL analysis (Johnston 2010).

However, when using these technical facilities, which opportunities arise for describing the sequential, simultaneous, and spatial dimension of SLs? Which major risks and shortcomings are accompanied by using them?

Following the best practice approach, I show along some main aspects – done within our Austrian SL research, which good/best practices provide linguistic and social benefits for SL analyses. These outcomes lead to ethnic and linguistic guidelines which I introduce as recommendations for describing, analyzing and using SL data. The following main aspects will be illustrated by examples and will serve as a basis for future guidelines:

(A) SL description requires the data of several SL users to show the Deaf community use.

(B) SL annotation requires the insider view and thus is to be done by Deaf annotators.

(C) SL analysis requires the inclusion of all parameters of a signed discourse within the annotation and analysis process in order not to distort the analysis.

(D) Lexicon analysis requires semantic analysis from the signs' view.

(E) The SL description serves as a starting point, in other words, be careful when applying a grammatical framework as practically all of them date from spoken/written language analysis.

(F) Publications of the findings are also to be carried out in the investigated SL to access the outcome to the Deaf community.

Design-Based Research in Deaf Math Education – Exploring Cube Nets in German Sign Language (DGS)

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Design Based Research (DBR) is a core methodology in the educational sciences (Wittmann 2013). It is used to simultaneously design learning environments and to develop theories. DBR starts with a recognition of the design problem in education, such as a lack of teaching materials in German Sign Language (DGS). To suggest the solution and to derive design principles, DBR turns to theories. For solutions which implement DGS integration of theoretical aspects from didactics of mathematics and linguistics of Sign Languages is needed. The created learning environment can be tested and evaluated in educational settings. The outcome of the DBR is twofold: the concrete learning environments which aim to provide educational materials in DGS as well as new theoretical knowledge about the use of Sign Languages in teaching of geometry. The learning environment CUBE-NETS as a main outcome of our study contains videos with descriptions of cube-nets, set of problems in DGS and German, which can be solved with construction kits like *Polydron* or just by operation with mental images. At the same time, created videos can be viewed as data which can be analyzed to reveal new knowledge about teaching geometry. Knowledge about observed handling classifiers (Suppala 1982) can be used as strategies to solve mathematical problems. For example, signs for 'folding' and 'unfolding' as handling classifiers can help to move from actions with real life models to operations with mental images.

***From Classroom to Community:
Supporting Early-Career ISL Interpreters in their Transition.***
Katie McLoughlin
Trinity College

This research explores how early-career ISL interpreters are navigating the profession during their transition from classroom to community. It explores their experiences stepping into the profession, what types of support this group of interpreters want and what kind of training they feel they need. Through a mixed methods approach, this research compiles data from an anonymous online survey to identify the areas interpreters are in need of support.

The research findings highlight feelings of apprehensiveness when accepting assignments, an unreadiness in taking their first steps into the community and experiencing an overall sense of unsupported-ness when transitioning from the safe-space of the classroom into the unfamiliar territory of the profession. Based on these findings, this study concludes with recommendations of a more stable, supportive transitioning experience for early-career ISL interpreters through demographic-specific training of which is in alignment with what early-career ISL interpreters want.

Thursday, July 23, 2025: Poster Session Three

Mapping the Cognitive Structure of Sign Language through fMRI and Machine Learning: A Study on Visual-Linguistic Iconicity and Thought

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Most linguistic studies of sign languages have focused on labeling, vocabulary formation, and structural comparison with spoken languages to establish their linguistic legitimacy. However, relatively few have examined the relationship between sign language and thought, especially in terms of iconicity and cognitive mapping. This study aims to investigate the shared structural processes between language and thought using a neuroscientific approach, and to develop a learning model that reflects the visual-linguistic iconicity inherent in sign languages.

We conducted fMRI experiments to examine cortical activation during a sign language comprehension task and a set of non-verbal mental tasks. Eighteen native Japanese Sign Language (JSL) signers participated (12 Deaf, 6 CODAs). In the language task, participants viewed highly iconic JSL storytelling videos characterized by frequent use of classifier constructions and visual vernacular techniques—narrative forms emphasizing spatial mapping, constructed action, and bodily enactment. In the mental task, participants completed 50 illustrated visual reasoning quizzes, including cartoon completion, analogical reasoning, mental rotation, sequential reasoning, and figure completion. All tasks were visually presented and non-verbal.

Results showed significant activation in the left frontal and bilateral temporal regions—areas commonly associated with syntactic and integrative processing—during both the sign language and cartoon completion tasks. This suggests shared neural processing for discourse comprehension across verbal and non-verbal domains. In this study, we define verbal domains as structured linguistic input based on JSL narratives (including grammar, classifier predicates, and spatial syntax), and non-verbal domains as structured visual information without conventional linguistic form, such as interpreting causal sequences in silent cartoons. The overlapping activation patterns indicate that the brain may engage similar inferential and integrative mechanisms across these modalities. Notably, signal change was significantly higher in the cartoon condition, suggesting processing selectivity not attributable to general task difficulty.

We define cognitive iconicity as the mental alignment between the visual-spatial form of a sign and the conceptual structure it represents—such as spatial relations, causal logic, or object interaction—often realized through classifier constructions and embodied depiction. Based on these insights, we are developing a computational sign language learning model not through symbolic natural language processing (e.g., Hidden Markov Models), but through image-based retrieval and story-level visual reasoning techniques. This approach reflects the iconic and spatially structured nature of sign language, aligning more closely with the way meaning is encoded and retrieved in signed discourse.

This poster presents our integrated approach combining fMRI analysis with machine learning to explore the cognitive-linguistic foundations of sign language acquisition.

This study was funded by the Nippon Foundation and NPO Comekko.

From Gloss to Structure: A Modular Approach to the STS Corpus

**Nikolaus Riemer-Kankkonen
Stockholms Universitet**

International Sign version

https://signuistics.se/nikrkankkonen/3min_abstract_nrk_video.html

Plural expression in Estonian Sign Language

Jari Pärigma
Tallinna Ülikool

Goal. The paper presentation provides an overview of the numerical system in Estonian Sign Language with special focus on the plural expression as lexical and grammatical categories.

Questions. This paper addresses two research questions: 1) How are the numbers as lexical signs expressed? 2) How do nouns and verbs express the plural as a grammatical number category?

Methodology. The study involved 40 deaf signers subgrouping into several sociolinguistical variation such as age, gender, residence, attended school, age of acquisition. The data collection were conducted in Tartu, Narva and Tallinn with participants aged 18 to 80.

Discussion. The numeral system and plural expression in Estonian Sign Language (EVK) have previously been studied by Hollmann (2016) and Miljan (2002). Hollmann found that one-handed numerals (1–9) were predominantly used by younger signers. However, this study shows that young signers also continue to use the two-handed system. The methodology is novel in the Estonian context, employing structured elicitation stimuli not used in earlier studies. Based on data from 40 signers, this study provides a substantially broader empirical foundation than previous research, which included only 2–4 participants. In contrast to earlier research, this study also considers the role of buoys and reciprocals in plural expression, providing new insights into their function in Estonian Sign Language. Furthermore, it offers a detailed account of movement variation in the numerals 15–19.

SignBank 2.0.: Easy to Use, Easy to Administer and Easy to Share

Peter Romanek^{1,2}, Christian Rathmann^{1,2}, Ronice Müller de Quadros³, Francisco Fernandes⁴, Sther Condé⁴

Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin¹, Tallinna ülikool², Universidade Federal da Santa Catarina³, Levante Lab⁴

Lexical databases such as signbanks are essential tools for the lexical documentation of sign languages in the digital age. In recent decades, efforts in lexical documentation—often inspired by advancements in corpus linguistics—have led to the development of systems, toolkits, and processes for recording lexical, phonological, and morphological information about signs. In this context, *Signbank 2.0 for Sign Languages* (Quadros et al., 2024) was developed to enhance the functionality and scope of the Global Signbank (Crasborn et al., 2018).

The improved design of the web-based Signbank 2.0 emerged from a collaborative effort between linguists and developers, with active involvement from end-users throughout the design and development process. The project reflects the principles of Digital Humanities and incorporates a Deaf-centered perspective. Its key outcomes include:

- Decentralized administrative rights through role-based access control
- Institutional decentralization by engaging new institutions in the management and preservation of Signbank 2.0
- Reduced dependence on dedicated IT support
- Direct machine-readability of annotated sign language data
- Two-level search functionality: bidirectional sign search and search within annotated files

Signbank 2.0 has been implemented for International Sign, German Sign Language, Austrian Sign Language, and Estonian Sign Language. This development process provided a unique opportunity to reconsider the role of signbanks in language documentation as part of a broader ecosystem of language resources. It also enabled the creation of documentation practices that require minimal linguistic or technical expertise, ensuring the sustainable and accessible use of Signbank 2.0 for a wide range of users.

Deaf Mediators, Interpreters and Translators: Deaf access by Deaf people

Britta Durczok¹, Christian Peters¹, Christian Rathmann¹, Christopher Stone² & Jeremie Segouat³

¹ Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, ² University of Wolverhampton, ³ Université Toulouse Jean Jaurès

The DMIT research project investigates the professional scope, methodologies, processes, and strategies employed by Deaf mediators, interpreters, and translators (DMIT) in France, the United Kingdom, Germany, and across Europe. Drawing on online surveys and semi-structured interviews with DMIT practitioners, it examines working environments and task-specific demands. A multilingual, multimodal corpus—comprising translations and interpreted texts in British Sign Language (BSL), Langue des Signes Française (LSF), and Deutsche Gebärdensprache (DGS)—is annotated for (but not limited to) prosodic cues, temporal information, gaze behaviors, and iconic properties. Complementary psycholinguistic measures, including comprehension assessments and eye-tracking, reveal how the interpreting and translation products can be optimized for Deaf audiences. Together, these data establish evidence-based best practices and yield targeted recommendations for DMIT training curricula, continuing professional development, and language policy, thereby advancing translation and interpreting studies.

Thursday, July 24, 2025: Poster Session Four

Sign language-oriented learning and teaching of elementary algebra

Flavio Angeloni

Leibniz-Universität Hannover

The dissertation investigates the learning and teaching of elementary algebra in a sign language, with the focus on Austrian sign language (ÖGS). Algebra is a fundamental area of mathematics and the concept of variables is the basis for the introduction to algebra and for learning advanced mathematics. The dissertation includes a classification of variables as object, placeholder, symbols in calculations and shells. Iconicity and the nature of the relations between signs can influence the learning of mathematics in a sign language. Therefore, on the theoretical basis of the Peirce semiotics, these are the two further focal points of the dissertation. The study investigates (1) which signs deaf people use to refer to the variables, what iconicity they exhibit and what relations exist between these signs. In addition, (2) the relations between the signs of school students about variables are examined. To investigate the first research question, focus group discussions were conducted in ÖGS with adult deaf people solving task packages and videotaped. To investigate the second research question, a case study with three deaf students was conducted. They participated in a series of videotaped lessons in ÖGS in which the variable concept was introduced using a model with matchboxes for variables and matches for numbers. The video data was evaluated according to qualitative content analysis. Various ÖGS signs were recorded that are used in the discourse about variables and express different facets of the respective variable aspect. The relations between the recorded signs were visualised in a framework with the shell aspect in the centre. The results on iconicity are aligned with semiotic theory. The method is reflected upon in terms of the extent to which the determined syntagmatic framework is stable across different samples and which influence the model using with matchboxes can have.

Sociolinguistic Variability in Slovak Sign Language

Roman Vojtechovský
Trnava University

This poster provides an overview of research on sociolinguistic variability in Slovak Sign Language as utilised by the deaf community in Slovakia. It highlights key findings regarding sociolinguistic variability in Slovak Sign Language through studies of sign languages. This poster demonstrates that signs used by Slovak users differ based on age, region, the territory of schools for pupils with hearing impairments, religion, and gender. In parallel, it presents finger spelling employed by Slovak users in various kindergartens and primary schools for children and pupils with hearing impairments. We combined two methods to investigate the following social factors: collecting sign language data by excerpting from published dictionaries and analysing several video recordings of sign language communication by signers of different ages on Facebook. Additionally, we elicited signs from individual deaf signers. This poster also showcases signs excerpted from dictionaries that appear to be from the 20th century, in contrast to those from the 21st century. We applied the method of collecting sign language data by excerpting from published dictionaries. Our research indicates that the most prevalent social factor influencing lexical variability in Slovak Sign Language is the intergenerational difference among signers, observable in three generations: younger, middle-aged, and older. The second significant social factor is the lexical variability of signing, which results from the territories of primary schools for pupils with hearing impairments and kindergartens for children with hearing impairments. Less common social factors include lexical variability among signers from different regions of Slovakia and signers belonging mainly to two religious communities (Catholics and Jehovah's Witnesses). Finger spelling can vary among signers. We were unable to gather data on gender differences in signing, as participants were uncertain whether such differences existed between male and female signers. This poster represents an initial exploration into the collection of linguistic data on Slovak Sign Languages, which display variability depending on the social context within the community of sign language users.

Are depictive constructions in Norwegian Sign Language similar in syntactic characteristics to ideophones in spoken languages?

Felicia Bisnath¹, Benjamin Anible²

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Introduction: Linguistic signs may depict or mimic the actual properties of referents (Haiman 1980, Perniss et al. 2010). Depictive signs contrast with descriptive ones which use labels to identify referents. Ideophones are a conventionalised class of marked words that depict sensory imagery found in some spoken languages (Dingemanse 2012). In Japanese, the morphosyntactic characteristics of ideophones vary based on their level of expressivity (Dingemanse & Akita 2017). Specifically, the greater the expressivity, the less likely an ideophone is to appear as a predicate. In contrast to spoken languages, depiction is pervasive in signed languages (Wilcox 2004) and more ad hoc than ideophones. Furthermore, some concepts can be represented descriptively or depictively, and depictive and descriptive strategies can be used simultaneously (Ferrara & Johnston 2014).

Research Question: We ask if depictive constructions in signed languages have similar morphosyntactic properties to ideophones in spoken languages by investigating syntactic properties of descriptive and depictive constructions in the Norwegian Sign Language (NTS) corpus (Ferrara in preparation).

Method: Our data comes from retellings of Herr Jakob comics in the NTS corpus by 18 signers from Bergen, Trondheim and Oslo. Each signer retold 2 of 4 comics. We coded descriptive and depictive constructions for their status as arguments and predicates following Ferrara & Johnston (2014). Descriptive constructions are primarily identified by their resemblance to citation forms as specified in the lexical database (Norwegian Signbank), and secondarily by Norwegian mouthing (Ferrara in preparation). Depictive constructions are those involving classifier handshapes and constructed action. We assume the following expressivity hierarchy: descriptive < classifier construction < constructed action.

Expected findings and conclusion: Given the pervasiveness of depiction in signed languages, we expect that predicates and arguments will not be significantly associated with descriptive or depictive strategies. This study contributes to understanding the interplay of depiction and description cross-modally and assesses the utility of extrapolating findings about ideophones in spoken languages to depiction in signed languages.

Experiences of Deaf people and hearing sign language interpreters with feedback and or criticism

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This poster presentation builds upon Ortíz Domínguez's (2024) bachelor thesis exploring audism, racism, and hearing and white privilege dynamics. The initial study investigated BIPoC individuals experiences confronting white people about racist behaviours, extending this analysis to Deaf-hearing interactions. Using group interview data, the research identified resistance patterns and proposed a framework parallel to white fragility. Findings revealed hearing individuals lack awareness regarding their privilege, responding defensively through argumentation, denial of Deaf expertise, avoidance, and centring their emotional reactions. Notably, Deaf participants reported that hearing sign language interpreters exhibited the most negative responses to feedback and criticism. This unexpected finding motivated the current investigation examining how hearing sign language interpreters respond to feedback and criticism from Deaf people. The theoretical framework examines interpreter privileges to illuminate power dynamics and dependency relationships, and exploring how feedback acceptance can enhance communication and collaboration. The central research question asks: *"How do sign language interpreters cope with feedback and criticism, and what strategies do they employ?"*. The study employs a mixed-methods approach. An online survey containing semi-standardised questionnaire will be distributed to hearing sign language interpreters. The survey will examine their experiences with feedback and criticism, stress levels, emotional responses and strategies for handling their feelings, as well as the effect on community engagement. The data will be analysed using either R or SPSS. Additionally, an online platform will allow Deaf individuals to submit video and written testimonials sharing their perspectives without structured constraints. Inspirational prompts will be provided, and these will acknowledge the individuals priorities and concerns. Signed videos will be transcribed and analysed using MAXQDA through thematic narrative analysis. This study aims to foster mutual understanding, highlight the emotional labour involved in providing feedback, and support interpreters in developing more constructive, community-centred responses.

Easy German Sign Language: Comprehension, Production and Translation

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This study evaluates the comprehensibility of Easy DGS–translated video texts through two complementary investigations. The first one conducted an online survey Deaf respondents with cognitive disabilities (n = 8) rated six items including but not limited to comprehensibility, signing speed, and the perceived importance of Easy DGS—on a five-point Likert scale. Results via frequency analysis will be discussed. The second one focuses on videotaped focus group sessions with Deaf experts with cognitive disabilities. The first part solicited feedback on Easy DGS videos, while the second one engaged participants in viewing varied genres and producing signed texts across discourse modes, followed by reflective discussion on their needs and preferences.

All data were annotated in ELAN and analyzed within the framework qualitative content analysis.

Key findings suggest the list of criteria for translation of Easy DGS texts:

- Structure multiple topics using buoys, constructed action, dialogue, and character perspectivae;
- Salient facial expressions to support comprehension;
- High presence of predicates in signed utterances

Despite limited sample sizes, the results affirm the importance of Easy DGS for accessible information delivery and support the list of recommendations for its text translation and production.

Sign Language Platform: Portal, Creation of Materials, Learning & Teaching, Assessment and Interpreting & Translation

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VisuoLab is an open-access, multilingual, and multimodal platform developed for deaf and sign language communities. Built with input from teachers, researchers, and deaf professionals, VisuoLab offers visually-centered tools for sign language teaching, learning, assessment, interpretation, translation, and research. It emphasizes accessibility, usability, and community involvement.

The platform features five core moduls:

Sign Language Portal: A repository of videobooks, teaching resources, glossaries, and academic publications, integrated with sign language corpora and SignBank.

Creation and Publication of Sign Language materials: Users can produce and publish content such as videobooks, glossaries, and instructional materials in sign language.

Interactive Classroom: Supports online and blended education in Sign Languages, Deaf Studies, and Interpreting/Translation.

Sign Language Assessment: A space for media and conference interpreting in sign languages.

Signbank 2.0 for Sign Languages: A web-based platform for lexical documentation.

VisuoLab supports several written languages (English, German, Portuguese, Spanish, Estonian) and sign languages (including International Sign, German Sign Language, Libras, and Estonian Sign Language). It allows users to create and share sign language content, conduct assessments, and provide feedback directly on videos. Tools also support interpreting/translation practice by enabling source-target language video production with interactive feedback.

The platform fosters collaborative learning, offering tools for both students and instructors to engage in sign-based classroom activities. Integrated linguistic resources—such as corpora, glossaries, and grammars—enhance research and teaching.

VisuoLab's design reflects the visual culture of deaf communities and aims to preserve and expand sign language documentation. By enabling content creation and sharing in sign language, it serves as a comprehensive resource for language education, professional training, and cultural preservation.